

Factors Influencing Implementation of Partnership-Funded Projects At Kenya Electricity Transmission Company (KETRACO) In Kenya

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Abstract:

Electricity transmission infrastructure and associated substations in Kenya are the most important assets any country can have as it aid in terms of evacuation of power from points of generation either by Kenya Electricity Generation company (Kengen) or Geothermal Development Company (GDC) to points of off-take for purposes of access to the electricity by locals in collaboration with Kenya Power (KP), system reinforcements of the existing grid, regional interconnections that enables Kenya to do power trade with other countries in East and Central Africa etc. Availability of power is essential especially now that Kenyas' economy needs it as a prerequisite in its quest to fulfill one of the big four agenda of Industrialization. The sole government organization that is mandated to carry out the planning, designing, constructing, owning and maintaining the transmission infrastructure is Kenya Electricity Transmission Company (KETRACO) and it has considerably done well in delivering the projects. However, the implementation of the said projects have had a fair share of challenges and criticism over its failure to start a project, delays to start, taking extremely longer times to complete a project, objection by the community affected by the project, contractors pulling out from the project, overhead charges/penalties by the contractors which caused partners to hold funds until their conditions are met and failure by the organization to have sound implementation team in the project, which have impacted negatively on projects progress. The general objective of the study is to establish the factors influencing the implementation of project management in Partnership-funded projects at KETRACO. This was done by looking at Influence of Project Planning, Stakeholders' Involvement, Technical Skills of the project implementation team and Management Leadership of the projects. A descriptive research design was used. The target population was all the on-going transmission lines and associated Substations projects by Kenya Electricity Transmission Company in Kenya with an accessible population that comprised of 19 project managers and 25 project engineers and 10 Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) facility heads. A census approach was utilized thus the study had 54 respondents. A pilot study was conducted to test the validity and reliability of data collection instrument. Data was collected through questionnaires and interviews. Questionnaires were used to collect data from project managers and engineers whereas interviews were used for community facility heads. Out of the 54 respondents targeted by the study 45 responded achieving response rate of 83.3%. The findings revealed that project planning, stakeholders' involvement and management leadership had positive and statistically significance influence on the implementation of project management before and after incorporating moderating variable. Technical skills had positive but statistically insignificance influence on the implementation of project management before and after incorporating moderating variable. The study recommended that project planning should start at initial stage of concept development where the team should come up with master plan which needs to be reviewed regularly. In addition, policies should be put in place to ensure that stakeholders are involved in all projects developments and locals are given opportunities to actively participate in activities that may not require technical skills. The study further recommends that future researchers might as well adopt a case study research design for other sector other than energy sector that would further add value in understanding the factors affecting the implementation of partnership-funded projects

Key words: Project Planning, Stakeholder Involvement, Management Leadership, Technical Skills, Partnership-funded Projects Implementation

I. INTRODUCTION

A project is a unique and transient endeavor undertaken to attain planned objectives that can be outlined in terms of outputs, outcomes or benefits. A project is usually deemed to be a success if it achieves the objectives according to their acceptance criteria, within an agreed timescale and budget, (PMBOK 2014). Project is regarded a success when project management are well implemented. Implementation of partnership-funded projects involves taking into account the following three subdivisions; Project Processes (Initiation, Planning, Execution, Monitoring and Controlling and Closure), Project Lifecycles (Concept Phase, Planning Phase, Execution Phase and Close Out Phase), Project Management Systems (entails components such as Human, Cultural, Organizational, Methodological, Information, Planning and Control/ Management) to achieve predetermined goals and meet specific success criteria. Project management methods have been extensively used by many public and private entities to solve their problems, manage scarce resources and, achieve important objectives.

In USA, Morris (2012) established in a research that was carried out at Oxford and early 1980s showed that many of the factors that cause projects not to meet their schedule or value targets are not covered by the PMBOK kind model. He went on to mention that, "Much of the PMBOK material is helpful in managing projects, but is not sufficient to manage them with success. This should be no surprise as focusing on execution alone, without due consideration to context and strategy, will invariably lead either to inappropriately selected objectives or in optimal strategies for accomplishing them. The Standish Group 2004 Report indicated that the main reason for project failure (in developed countries) is not the absence of general resources or financial resources, but the lack of Project management capability (Malan et al., 2015). Further, in first world countries external conditions such as market and politics are less important for the success of projects (Torp, Austeng, 2014).

Partnership-funded projects implementation in developing countries in Africa is highly influenced by their external environment (Jekale, 2014). Moreover, the project environment is unstable and characterized by rapid change of markets, shift of funding sources, frequent change of government policies and the business environment. In addition, projects in those countries are affected by prevalence of corruption, war, drought and governments political priorities (Alutu and Udhawuve, 2013). For example in

Nigeria, the cost of construction materials was reported to have shown a 400% increase over a period of two years because of change in government policies (devaluation of its currency and inflation) (Sonuga et al., 2012). The presence of only three PMI chapters in Africa countries attest to the value and attention given to project management in developing countries. Further, according to (Nguyen, 2007), many of the efforts to transfer project management knowledge and technology to developing countries were not successful mainly due to : lack of support of senior management and a perception that project management methodology is not applicable in developing countries.

Implementation of partnership-funded projects in Kenya begun with vision 2030 and is expected that vision 2030 can transform the project management process in Kenya. Prior to vision 2030, projects in Kenya that had been initiated by the government institutions did not seem to hold water and most of the time they collapsed or took considerably long periods of time to be completed (Mwaura et al., 2014). For a project that will affect the community directly or indirectly during implementation to be successful, the organization needs to come with a structure that is peopling centered and recognizes them (Mwaura, 2014). In a study conducted by the Institute of Economic Affairs (2012), it indicated that part of the budget of the turn-key projects implemented by government institutions must be set aside for the communities in the affected areas where implementation of their funded projects are undertaken. With such initiatives woven into the society, the community will feel the inclusivity in the rollout of projects as well as contributes towards community ownership of projects.

Due to the inability of the government to fund the all transmission projects, it has allowed partners to contribute to the funding process (Afande, 2017). This initiative by the partners has however been faced with a number of setbacks. One major setback is the poor training of the employees that the government institution offers to manage the funds and projects and this leads to loss, misappropriation or misuse of funds. Leadership in Project to make it a success is a key project management issue, but still poorly defined in terms of its concept and paths necessary to achieve it (Njenga, 2017).

Statement of the Problem

Auditor Generals' report of 2018 put Kenya Electricity Transmission Company (KETRACO) on the spot after it raised a red flag over an approval made by the management of an estimated Kshs.3.8 Billion being payment of idling fees charged by contractor for his 100% workforce and equipment for a period of 21 months that construction of Mombasa-Nairobi transmission line was stalled by the Project Affected Persons (PAPs) over different compensation rates applied on limited use of land in one area as well none-inclusion of the community to work on casual terms. A case of improper planning and scheduling of Kshs.17 Billion Mombasa-Nairobi transmission line project was witnessed too whereby wayleave corridor acquisition and subsequent construction of approximately 450 kilometers started way back in 2010 and took 7 years to be completed and commissioned instead of the planned 3 years. An almost replica in terms of delay is a maiden Loiyangalani-Suswa transmission line and associated Substations project that costed a total of KSh.28 Billion that suffered a tremendous delay that attracted fines of upto Kshs.5.6 Billion which according to the management, the delays arose from termination of the initial contractor who pulled out after declaring a state of bankruptcy. Over and above, it is not clear whether management, through prescribed procurement procedures, satisfied themselves that the initial contractor was technically and financially qualified for the job before award of the contract. An internal audit report raised queries over different quotations invoiced by contractors for daily allowances of their technical staff working alongside KETRACO's project managers and engineers as site managers and supervisors. Rates for similar professionals that the company has in its workforce, for instance, an expatriate site manager for Kalpataru earned about KSh100, 000 per week, while KEC and L&T were charging KSh200, 000 per day to do a similar job. This study sought to examine factors that influence the implementation of partnership funded projects at KETRACO that includes project planning, stakeholder involvement, influence of technical skills as well as management leadership.

General Objective

The general objective of the study is to establish the factors influencing the implementation of partnership-funded projects at Kenya Electricity Transmission Company (KETRACO).

Specific Objectives

- i. To assess the influence of project planning on the implementation of partnership funded projects.
- ii. To assess the influence stakeholders' involvement on the implementation of partnership funded projects.
- iii. To establish the influence of technical skills on the implementation of partnership funded projects.
- iv. To determine the influence of management leadership on the implementation of partnership funded projects.

Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: Project planning has no statistically significant influence on the implementation of partnership-funded projects at KETRACO

H₀₂: Stakeholders' involvement has no significant influence on the implementation of partnership-funded projects at KETRACO.

H₀₃: Technical skills have no significant influence on the implementation of partnership-funded projects in KETRACO.

H₀₄: Management leadership has no significant influence on the implementation of partnership-funded projects in KETRACO.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Theory of Planning

Theory of planning was introduced by Andreas Faludi in 1973 where planning is defined as the application of scientific methods in policy making. The approach makes a difference between Theory in planning (substantive theory) which helps planners to understand their area of concern and Theory of planning (procedural theory) which helps planners understand themselves and their operating methods. It is also noted the theory in planning and theory of planning are both needed for effective planning (Mukhopadhyay & Faludi, 2015).

The theory of planning follows three main stages: Conceptualization where there is a managerial part and an effectors part in the project, the primary function of the managerial part is planning and the primary function of the effector part is to translate the resultant plan into action. The second is principles which entail the current state of the world, the desired goal state and the allowable transformations of state that can be achieved by actions, a series of actions from where a plan can be deduced. The plan

is translated into reality by the effector part of the organization. Finally, the assumptions which are: translating a plan into action is a simple process, by following directions and the internal planning of a task is a matter of the person to whom the task has been assigned.

Planning should therefore focus on structuring the environment to contribute to purposeful acting. The look-ahead planning aims at alignment of plan and situation. Should represents the tasks in the plan, while Can represents those tasks that realistically will be possible to start in the situation. Thus, look-ahead planning subscribes to the view of human action as situated - a foundational assumption of managing-as organizing, while also acknowledging the significance of plans for action, as advocated by managing, as planning (Koskela& Howell, 2002). In this study, the theory of planning was used to test hypothesis 1.

Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder management theory is an organization management theory that was developed by Edward Freeman in the year 1983 to explain who and what really counts in an organization. Stakeholder management theory states that there are several parties who have the capacity to affect the performance of business that that they are in contest to add value for themselves in an organization. The theory argues that not only the managers or owners of an organization matter but the success in an organization is based on fulfilling the interest of all stakeholders in an organization. The theory outlines that owners, managers, employees, customers, suppliers, communities and government entities are some of the key stakeholders in an organization. The theory further states that the management team of an organization should try as much as possible to balance its satisfaction of various demands and interests of stakeholders (Kamanga and Steyn, 2013).

This theory assumes that all the interests of diverse stakeholders can at best be balanced (Opuch, 2016). Kwatsima (2014) criticized stakeholder's theory based on this assumption by arguing that an organization reaps maximum benefits from its stakeholders not on balancing their interests but through constant negotiation and the level of patriotism or loyalty towards the organization. This theory has however in the recent past used to explain how the management team seeks to satisfy the interest of various stakeholders as well as control their influence to the organization (Simon, 2017)

In this study, the theory was relevant in explaining how KETRACO involved the community as they are the main stakeholders towards implementation of transmission line projects. In this context, KETRACO identified stakeholders in person, analyze their power versus interest, commit to them and engage them accordingly. The negotiation with the stakeholders inspired loyalty among them to maximally contribute towards easement thus faster implementation of transmission line projects. This theory was therefore relevant in guiding study in establishing the role of stakeholder involvement on implementation of partnership-funded projects. This theory was used to test hypothesis 2 of this study.

Human Capital Theory

The concept of human capital was fully developed in the 1960s and states that the human factor in the organisation; the combined intelligence, skills and expertise that gives the organisation its distinctive character. The human elements of the organisation are those that are capable of learning, changing, innovating and providing the creative thrust which if properly motivated can ensure the long-term survival of the organization as well as her projects as cited by Thomas et al (2013). Such a thought results in the conclusion that the build-up of exceptionally gifted people isn't enough for the organization, there must also be a desire on the part of individuals to utilize their skills and continuous knowledge within the organization and their position. Skills in this context will cater for the technical skills that the project implementation team must at least possess.

Human capital is generally understood to consist of the individual's capabilities, knowledge, skills and experience of the company's employees and managers. Investment in human capital includes formal education, off-the-job training and on-the-job training to impart required technical skills (Jones et al 2012). According to Jones et al (2012), skills can be acquired through education and (formal) training but also (and mainly) through the course of people's activities at work (learning-by-doing). Most specific job skills are learned from performing the work activities themselves. Apprenticeship and work experience, according to his argument, has no known perfect substitute. Learning potential is viewed as a by-product of the work surrounding, tied to a specific work activity, but varying from activity to activity and from job to job. From educating and training an employee including the experience amassed from, generates an unmatched stock of productive capital. Job search and migration are activities that increase the value of one's human capital by increasing the price received for a given stock of skills. A manager's experience is measured in terms of time in years, past involvement and should reflect in the quality of his work (Mutai, 2017).

Management Leadership Theory

There exists a variety of views on leadership as there are characteristic that distinguish leaders from non-leaders. While most studies and researches has shifted from traits that are traditional or personality-based theories to a situational theories, which dictates that the situation in which leadership is exercised is determined by the leadership skills and characteristics of the leader (Avolio, Walumbwa, and Weber, 2017), all contemporary theories can fall under one of the following three perspectives: leadership as a method or relationship, leadership as a combination of traits or personality characteristics, or leadership as certain behaviors or, as they are more commonly referred to, leadership skills. In dominant theories of leadership, there exists the notion that, at least to some degree, leadership is a process that involves influence with a group of people toward the realization of goals (Wolinski, 2016).

Management leadership control has been considered as an important factor that influences the success of projects (Adams, 2017). Mockler (2015) considers control as a systematic effort made by organization's management to compare performance to predetermined standards and to undertake, if necessary, corrective actions to see that human and other corporate resources are being used in the most effective and efficient way possible in achieving an organization's objectives. A company's' management leadership control ensures the coordination and effective functioning of all activities, so that the formulated objectives are implemented and followed according to plan. All management functions may be carried out, in the sense that a project manager may plan, organize and give guidance, but he/she cannot ensure that the plans are carried out without exercising control.

Therefore, leadership control is critically important to ensure satisfactory progress in attaining the organization’s objectives and to make sure that the resources are used effectively (Brevis *et al.*, 2015).

Leadership control is important in projects because even the best plans may go wrong and thus control is exercised to ensure that, at all levels of the project, service delivery takes place according to plan and that the organization’s resources are distributed in a way that the projects goals are reached. Finally, leadership control in projects results in better quality management and enables organizations to cope with change and uncertainty (Brevis *et al.*, 2015), thus ensuring effective project performance. This theory was used to test hypothesis 4 of this study.

Conceptual Framework

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A research design refers to the methodological guidelines put in place for collecting and analyzing data, Saunder, Lews, and Thornhill (2009). This study used a descriptive research design to identify the relationship among the study’s variables. The descriptive research design is a design that gives the real description of an occurrence without treatment or control of the variables (Jankowicz, 2005). Descriptive study sought to obtain information that describes phenomena by asking individuals about their perceptions, attitudes, behavior or values, (Mugenda and Mugenda, 2003). it gave the researcher several research approaches as well as analysis to be incorporated and ability to gather in-depth data from study respondents (Sekaran, 2003).The study employed qualitative and quantitative approach to gather information as to how the KETRACO is implementing project management while quantitative approach was used to collect data on ideas and opinions of stakeholders in regard to project management. Both primary and secondary data were collected.

Target Population

Target population refers to all the members of a hypothetical or real group of subjects, objects or individuals to whom a researcher desires to generalize the conclusions of the study (Kothari, 2014). It is also defined as a group of objects or individuals that is of interest to the researcher due to commonality of characteristics of the members (Shirish, 2012). The target populations of the study were all the 19 on-going partnership-funded transmission projects and associated substations by KETRACO in Kenya as shown in Appendix V. The units of observation were therefore the 19 Project Managers heading each project, 25 Project Engineers and 10 CSR Facility heads.

Table 3.1: Sampling frame

	Frequency	Percentage
Project Managers	19	35.185%
Project Engineers	25	46.296%
CSR Facility Heads	10	18.5185%
Total	54	100.0%

Source: Kenya Electricity Transmission Company (2018)

Sampling Frame

A sampling frame as a list of members of the research population from which a random sample may be drawn (Kothari, 2014). A sampling frame should be large to allow the researcher to make inferences of the entire population (Silverman, 2015). Guided by this definition, the sampling frame for this study was as shown in Table

Sampling Technique

In this context, the census approach was best suited and adopted for this study because the population was fairly small. In a census, data is collected from every member of the population thus data was collected from 60 respondents of the on-going 19 partnership-funded transmission projects and associated substations in Kenya. 10% was used for pilot study which was excluded in the final study.

Data Collection Instrument

The data collection instruments refer to the tools used by a researcher to collect data for a study (Sekaran and Bougie, 2011). According to Greener (2008) primary data is the data collected directly from first hand occurrence which has not been exposed to processing or any other handling. This study used questionnaires and interviews for this purpose. Questionnaires are tools that consist of both open and closed ended questions in which the respondents are given options that they use to indicate their desired response to a question (Upagade and Shende, 2012). Researcher used questionnaires to collect data from Project managers and engineers whereas interviews were used for community facility heads. The cost efficiency and ease of analysis using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) was for some of the reasons why it was the preferred research tool for this study (Orodho, 2003). Likert scale questions on a five-point scale was used as measuring scale whereby a statement is assigned a value on extent of agreement to the statement. It allows a participant in a study to express how the extent to which they agree or disagree with a particular statement (Khan et al., 2011). It was advantageous to this study as respondents were able to address the questions with ease thus helped the study achieve a higher response rate (Mugenda and Mugenda, 2003). Further, it provided uniform responses and allowed qualitative data to be transformed into quantitative data which eased the data analysis process.

IV. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Descriptive Analysis

This section provides results and discussions of the findings and data analysis of the study using percentage frequencies per objective. The study sought to establish the extent the independent variables considered in the study affect implementation of partnership-funded projects at Kenya Electricity Transmission Company.

Influence of project planning on implementation of the Kenya Primary Education Development project

This section is in line with the first study objective which sought to establish the influence of project planning on implementation of the Kenya Primary Education Development project. The findings from the analysis were as shown in Table 1.0

Table 4.8: Descriptive statistics of Project Planning and Implementation of Partnership-Funded Projects

Statements	SD	D	NA/D	A	SA	Mean	STD
Planning of the project activities start from the project definition stage	0.0%	0.0%	31.1%	51.1%	17.8%	3.87	.69
The planning policies and procedures on the project planning are well understood for implementation	4.4%	22.2%	11.1%	57.8%	4.4%	3.36	1.03
The planning tools and techniques are well understood and properly used during project implementation	11.1%	17.8%	20.0%	35.6%	15.6%	3.27	1.25
The budget estimates in the project plan are adhered to during implementation	15.6%	31.1%	37.8%	15.6%	0.0%	2.53	.94

From the descriptive statistics results, most of the respondents, 68.9% agreed that planning of the project activities start from the project definition stage. 62.2% agreed that the planning policies and procedures on the project planning are well understood for implementation. On average 51.2% agreed that the planning tools and techniques are well understood and properly used during project implementation. Slightly lower than half 46.7% disagreed that the budget estimates in the project plan are adhered to during implementation. The study established that planning of the project activities start from the project definition stage where the planning policies and procedures are shared to relevant stakeholders in addition to planning tools and techniques even though the budget estimates in the project plan are not strictly adhered to during implementation. The findings are in line with Nyingi (2017), who noted that activities in project planning include the identification of the project's objective; the specification of project resources required and their respective allocation; and the determination of the formulas to be explored to deliver the project end product, respond to critical events and evaluate activities and outcomes

Stakeholder Involvement and Implementation of Partnership-Funded Projects

Objective two of the study sought to assess the influence stakeholders' involvement on the implementation of project management in partnership funded projects. In order to assess the influence of the stakeholders' involvement, the study sought to establish whether there is stakeholders do participate in project management and the extent of their participation in project management. In addition, results of descriptive statistics analysis are discussed below.

Table 4.11: Descriptive statistics of Stakeholder Involvement and Implementation of Projects

Statements	SD	D	NA/D	A	SA	Mean	STD
Active engagements of stakeholders' through the entire project cycle help to build and control stakeholder relationships.	0.0%	4.4%	8.9%	26.7%	60.0%	4.42	.84
Stakeholder involvement could lead effective implementation of projects	0.0%	0.0%	6.7%	42.2%	51.1%	4.44	.62
Project managers work with local people to create opportunities for local people to participate meaningfully in project activities.	0.0%	6.7%	46.7%	11.1%	35.6%	3.76	1.03
Review and analysis of stakeholders was undertaken when undertaking and implementing projects	0.0%	24.4%	48.9%	26.7%	0.0%	3.02	.72

From the descriptive statistics results, most of the respondents, 86.7% agreed that active engagements of stakeholders' through the entire project cycle help to build and control stakeholder relationships. A high percentage 93.3% agreed that stakeholder involvement could lead effective implementation of projects. On average 46.7% could not agree or disagreed that project manager's work with local people to create opportunities for local people to participate meaningfully in project activities. Further about half of the respondents 48.9% could not also agree or disagreed that review and analysis of stakeholders was undertaken when undertaking and implementing projects. The study established that even though there were active engagements of stakeholders which could lead effective implementation of projects the opportunities were not adequately created for local people to actively participate in various activities during implementation. According to Hofisi (2013), rural communities mostly fail to support projects if they were not adequately empowered by the project and that of funded projects can only be sustainable if they allow for participatory processes from identification to completion. It was observed that in as much as participatory projects were able to address the basic needs of the community through involvement of the community themselves, overambitious projects could sometimes be unsustainable. However, stakeholder involvement needs to be managed by care, too much stakeholder involvement could lead to undue influence on the evaluation, and too little could lead to evaluators dominating the process (Musomba et al, 2013). In addition, review and analysis of stakeholders was not adequately undertaken when undertaking and implementing projects. Kyriakopoulos (2011) noted that it is important to carry out frequent monitoring and perform focused reviews involving all the stakeholders in keeping the project on track.

Technical Skills and Implementation of Partnership-Funded Projects

Objective three of the study sought to establish the influence of technical skills on the implementation of project management in partnership-funded projects. In order to establish the influence of the technical skills, the study sought to find out whether technical skills are required to implement partnership-funded projects and to what extent they influence the implementation of projects. Further the study sought to find out whether the supply of human resource capacity is adequate for the implementation and sustainability of the projects. In addition, results of descriptive statistics analysis are discussed below.

Table 4.16: Descriptive statistics of Technical Skills on Implementation of Project Management

Statements	SD	D	NA/D	A	SA	Mean	STD
Technical skill is critical determinant of how project activities are carried out.	0.0%	0.0%	46.7%	35.6%	17.8%	3.71	.76
Project managers should have relevant experience or knowledge about the technology required by the project.	0.0%	0.0%	48.9%	17.8%	33.3%	3.84	.90
Project managers should possess technical competence in order to implement projects effectively	0.0%	0.0%	33.3%	33.3%	33.3%	4.00	.83
Project manager should be trained regularly on application of logic in order to perform their duties	0.0%	0.0%	31.1%	53.3%	15.6%	3.84	.67

From the descriptive statistics results, most of the respondents, slightly above half of the respondents 53.4% agreed that technical skill is critical determinant of how project activities are carried out. About half of the respondents 51.1% agreed that project

managers should have relevant experience or knowledge about the technology required by the project. 66.6% agreed that project managers should possess technical competence in order to implement projects effectively while 68.9% agreed that project manager should be trained regularly on application of logic in order to perform their duties. On average the study established that technical skills are important factors that influence effective implementation of partnership-funded projects at KETRACO even though not to the great extent. The finding of the study support earlier finding by Orvis (2017) who stated that the bottom line is technical competence (the ability to solve complex engineering or scientific problems) serves to enhance the project manager's credibility with customers, senior leadership and the project team. However it's not apparent that the project management's ability is the most vital requirement for project management capability

Management Leadership and Project Implementation of Partnership-Funded Projects

Objective four of the study sought to determine the influence of management leadership on the implementation of partnership-funded projects. In order to establish the influence of the management leadership, the study sought to establish whether leadership influences the implementation of partnership-funded projects and to what extent. Further the study sought to find out which leadership styles are applied by the management team. In addition, results of descriptive statistics analysis are discussed below.

Table 4.20: Descriptive statistics of Management Leadership and Partnership-Funded Projects Implementation

Statements	SD	D	NA/D	A	SA	Mean	STD
The project managers should be responsible for leading, building the skills of workers, encouraging innovation and empowering creative problem solving	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	48.9%	51.1%	4.51	.51
Leadership training is essential to project managers in order to increase efficiency in project management.	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	33.3%	66.7%	4.67	.48
Variety of leadership styles should be applied when dealing with different challenges during project implementation	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	33.3%	66.7%	4.67	.48
Lack of appropriate leadership affects project implementation and may lead to project failure	0.0%	0.0%	4.4%	46.7%	48.9%	4.44	.59

From the descriptive statistics results, all the respondents agreed that the project managers should be responsible for leading, building the skills of workers, encouraging innovation and empowering creative problem solving, leadership training is essential to project managers in order to increase efficiency in project management and variety of leadership styles should be applied when dealing with different challenges during project implementation. A high percentage 95.6% also agreed that lack of appropriate leadership affects project implementation and may lead to project failure. The study established that management leadership is a critical factor that influences the effective project implementation at KETRACO. The finding of the study reaffirm earlier finding by Shore (2015), who found out that leadership affects business process reengineering, systems design and development, software selection, implementation, and maintenance. He concluded that without appropriate leadership, the risk of project failure increases. Spears (2014), stated that leader serves by building the skills of followers, removing obstacles, encouraging innovation, and empowering creative problem solving

Funds Release Conditions

Funds Release Conditions was used by the study as a moderating factor to establish whether these conditions had influence on implementation of partnership-funded projects. The respondents were required to indicate the impact of impact of funds release conditions on implementation of partnership-funded projects. In addition, results of descriptive statistics analysis are discussed below.

Table 4.22: Descriptive statistics of Funds Release Conditions on Implementation of Partnership-Funded Projects

Statements	NE	SE	ME	LE	VLG	Mean	STD
Availability of a Conclusive ESIA Report to the partners	0.0%	0.0%	11.1%	11.1%	77.8%	4.67	.67
Availability of a No Objection report from the stakeholders (community) to the partners	0.0%	0.0%	15.6%	17.8%	66.7%	4.51	.76
Availability of the project viability report from the respective government institutions	0.0%	0.0%	15.6%	33.3%	51.1%	4.36	.74

Implementation of Partnership-funded projects

Implementation of Partnership-funded projects was considered to be that dependent variable of the study. The study intended to establish the level of implementation of partnership-funded projects. In addition, results of descriptive statistics analysis are discussed below.

Table 4.24: Descriptive statistics of Implementation of Partnership-funded projects

Statements	SD	D	NA/D	A	SA	Mean	STD
There is timely project execution on funded projects at KETRACO	8.9%	28.9%	46.7%	15.6%	0.0%	2.69	.85
The selection of the project team that is tasked with implementation of project management is done satisfactorily, on merit and competence	0.0%	15.6%	33.3%	51.1%	0.0%	3.36	.74
There is quality work done in the completed projects	0.0%	4.4%	8.9%	44.4%	42.2%	4.24	.80
There is proper & clear scope definition on projects done by KETRACO.	0.0%	0.0%	17.8%	64.4%	17.8%	4.00	.60
The projects done by KETRACO are constantly monitored and evaluated after the implementation.	0.0%	4.4%	20.0%	55.6%	20.0%	3.91	.76

From the descriptive statistic results, slightly below half of the respondents 46.7% could not agree or disagree whether there was timely project execution on partnership-funded projects at KETRACO. 51.1% agreed that the selection of the project team that is tasked with implementation of partnership-funded projects is done satisfactorily, on merit and competence. A high percentage 86.6% agreed that there is quality work done in the completed projects. 82.2% agreed that there is proper & clear scope definition on projects done by KETRACO. 75.6% agreed that the projects done by KETRACO are constantly monitored and evaluated after the implementation. The study established that Implementation of Partnership-funded projects met the quality standards and the selection of the project team was done satisfactorily, on merit and competence. However the projects are not normally completed on time as per the plan but there has been constantly monitored and evaluated after the implementation.

Results from the Interview

Community heads were interviewed to establish how the community leaders were selected, whether the community was involved during project construction, whether affected persons were adequately compensated for destroyed property or land used to erect towers among other key areas of interest from the community. The result findings from the interview revealed that the rationale used to select community representatives was mainly volunteers but in certain situation some members were nominated by KETRACO and at time members were elected through voting. The finding further revealed that KETRACO held community baraza before they started their project and gave the community opportunity to participate in determining the facilities they want to be constructed in their locality. The community heads concurred that KETRACO's project was successful because they involved the community in entirety. From the responses it was clear that community was involved to do manual work and hence was part of the project which ensured effective implementation of the projects.

The findings revealed that the community caused delay/ objected KETRACO's transmission line project for some reasons such as delay in payments of compensations of land use, failure to employ locals to carry out skilled labour and differential compensation for the same size of land use. From the interview responses the findings revealed that KETRACO compensation the community was not satisfactorily for destroyed property, land used to erect towers and some payments have not yet been effected even after completion of the projects, others were underpaid for the houses demolished, some people were paid differently for the same size

of land within same locality. Moreover, the community heads opined that KETRACO did a good thing to partner with the community during their projects implementation since it enabled them to construct their projects with ease. The findings further indicated that the facility that KETRACO constructed benefit the community and where some of the cited facilities include borehole, school and dispensary. In conclusion the community heads indicated that KETRACO management officially handed-over the facility to the community.

Multicollinearity Test

According to Kothari (2004), multicollinearity occurs when more than two predictor variables are inter-correlated. To test for multicollinearity, Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) or tolerance was used. Using the VIF method, a tolerance of less than 0.20 and a VIF of more than 5 indicates a presence of multicollinearity. If two or more variables have a Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) of five or above five, one of these variables ought to be removed from the regression analysis since this shows multicollinearity presence (Runkle *et al.*, 1994). The result of multicollinearity test is given in Table 4.25

Project Planning Practices and Implementation of PRIEDE project

The relationship between project planning practices and implementation of PRIEDE was analyzed where both variables were correlated and findings were as shown in Table 1.5.

Table 4.25: Multicollinearity Test Results

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)		
Project planning	.517	1.934
Stakeholders' involvement	.445	2.248
Technical skills	.830	1.205
Management leadership	.663	1.507

Normality Test on the Dependent Variable

To test for normality, the study employed the graphical method. The results from the graphical method are presented in the Figure 4.1

Inferential statistics

The general objective of the study is to establish the factors affecting the implementation of partnership-funded projects at Kenya Electricity Transmission Company (KETRACO). In order to achieve the objective of the study multiple regression analysis was conducted to establish the level of significance of the factors considered by the study at 5% level of significance. The results from the regression output were interpreted from the model summary, ANOVA and beta coefficient. The ordinary multiple regression was undertaken by considering all the variable and thereafter the effect of moderating variable (fund release conditions) was also established by conducting separate multiple regression analysis.

Multiple regression analysis

A multiple linear regression analysis between the study's dependent and independent variables was done. So as to carry out multiple regression analysis various items which measured every independent variable were weighted. Multiple linear regression analysis was afterward utilized to test whether there was interdependency between independent variables (project planning, stakeholders' involvement, technical skills and management leadership) and dependent variable (implementation of partnership-funded projects at KETRACO). The multiple regression analysis findings are discussed in Table 4.26 to Table 4.28.

Table 4.26: Model Summary for Implementation of Partnership-Funded Projects

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.797 ^a	.636	.599	.32002

a. Predictors: (Constant), Management leadership, Project planning, Technical skills, Stakeholders' involvement

The R value of 0.797 indicated that there was a linear correlation between project planning, stakeholders' involvement, technical skills and management leadership on implementation of partnership-funded projects at KETRACO. The value of R² showed the independent variables explanatory power of 0.636. This denotes that all the independent variables combined explain 63.6% of the changes in implementation of partnership-funded projects.

Table 4.27: ANOVA for Implementation of Partnership-Funded Projects

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	7.148	4	1.787	17.449	.000 ^b
Residual	4.096	40	.102		
Total	11.244	44			

a. Dependent Variable: Implementation of project management

b. Predictors: (Constant), Management leadership, Project planning, Technical skills, Stakeholders' involvement

The ANOVA showed an F statistic value of 17.449 at p-value of 0.000. This implies that the model was significant at 5% level of significance.

Table 4.28: Coefficients for Implementation of Partnership-Funded Projects

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-.401	.806		-.498	.621
Project planning	.188	.068	.369	2.779	.008
Stakeholders' involvement	.607	.159	.547	3.823	.000
Technical skills	.029	.062	.048	.459	.649
Management leadership	.406	.088	.540	4.613	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Implementation of Partnership-Funded Projects

The results of B coefficient indicated that there was a positive linear relationship between project planning, stakeholders' involvement, technical skills and management leadership with slopes of $\beta_1 = 0.188$, $\beta_2 = 0.607$, $\beta_3 = 0.029$ and $\beta_4 = 0.406$ respectively. This implies that holding all other variables constant, implementation of partnership-funded projects would increase by 0.188 units when project planning goes up by one unit, increase by 0.607 units when stakeholders' involvement goes up by one unit, increase by 0.029 units when technical skills goes up by one unit and increase by 0.406 when management leadership goes up by one unit. The multiple regression equation can be stated as shown:

$Y = -0.401 + 0.188X_1 + 0.607X_2 + 0.029X_3 + 0.406X_4 + \epsilon$ Where Y is implementation of partnership-funded projects while X_1 , X_2 , X_3 and X_4 represents project planning, stakeholder involvement, technical skills and management leadership respectively.

Moderating effect of Implementation of Partnership-Funded Projects

Additional multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to determine the moderating effect of fund release conditions on project planning, stakeholders' involvement, technical skills and management leadership and implementation of partnership-funded projects. The index for each independent variable determined using weighted average was multiplied by the moderating variable index and the resultant variables were regressed against the dependent variable. Aldwin (1994), noted that the moderation effect is normally expressed as an interaction between moderator and predictor variable. The results of the findings are as presented in Table 4.29 to 4.31

Table 4.29: Model Summary of Moderating variable on Implementation of Partnership-Funded Projects

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.803 ^a	.644	.609	.31623

a. Predictors: (Constant), Management leadership, Project planning, Stakeholders' involvement, Technical skills

From Table 4.29 above, it is clear that fund release conditions moderates the relationship between project planning, stakeholders' involvement, technical skills and management leadership since when moderated the independent variables are regressed against

implementation of partnership-funded projects R was 0.803 an increase from 0.797 while R^2 was 0.644 an increase from 0.636. This implies that the moderated model can explain 64.4% percent of the outcome up from 63.6% percent of implementation of partnership-funded projects which represents 0.8% increase. Further, R (correlation coefficient) changes from 0.797 to 0.803, an increase of 0.006.

Table 4.30: ANOVA of Moderating Variable on Implementation of Partnership-Funded Projects

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	7.244	4	1.811	18.111	.000 ^b
Residual	4.000	40	.100		
Total	11.244	44			

a. Dependent Variable: Implementation of partnership-funded projects

b. Predictors: (Constant), Management leadership, Project planning, Stakeholders' involvement, Technical skills

The results of ANOVA revealed that the entire model after introducing the moderating variable was significant with the F ratio = 18.111 at p Value $0.000 < 0.05$. This is an indication that the model can be relied upon.

Table 4.31: Coefficient Table of Moderating variable on Implementation of Project Management

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	-2.167	1.856		-1.168	.250
Project planning * Fund release condition	.333	.145	.653	2.298	.027
Stakeholders' involvement * Fund release condition	.667	.168	.601	3.972	.000
Technical skills * Fund release condition	.417	.384	.302	1.086	.284
Management leadership * Fund release condition	.583	.169	.776	3.444	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Implementation of Partnership-funded projects

Coefficient Table 4.31 presents the beta coefficients of the resulting model after introducing moderating variable fund release condition which indicated that project planning, stakeholders' involvement, technical skills and management leadership had positive effect on Implementation of partnership-funded projects with slopes of $\beta_1 = 0.333$, $\beta_2 = 0.667$, $\beta_3 = 0.417$ and $\beta_4 = 0.583$ respectively. This implies that holding all other variables constant, implementation of partnership-funded projects would increase by 0.333 units when project planning goes up by one unit, increase by 0.667 units when stakeholders' involvement goes up by one unit, increase by 0.417 units when technical skills goes up by one unit and increase by 0.583 when management leadership goes up by one unit. The multiple regression equation can be stated as shown:

$Y = -2.167 + 0.333X_1 + 0.667X_2 + 0.417X_3 + 0.583X_4 + \epsilon$ Where Y is implementation of partnership-funded projects while X_1 , X_2 , X_3 and X_4 represents project planning, stakeholder involvement, technical skills and management leadership respectively. From the findings of the study, it is clear that the introduction of the moderating variable (fund release condition) had an impact on project planning, stakeholders' involvement, technical skills as reflected by changes in B coefficient.

Review of Implementation of Partnership-Funded Projects after introduction of moderating variable.

The aim of introducing moderating factor was to establish the effect of the moderating variable (Fund release condition) of project planning, stakeholders' involvement, technical skills and management leadership on implementation of partnership-funded projects at KETRACO. The study revealed that the independent variables had positive effect before and after introduction of moderating variable correlation coefficient (R) changed from 0.797 to 0.803, an increase of 0.006. In addition, coefficient of determination (R^2) increased from 0.636 to 0.644 which implied after introducing moderating same variables explain 64.4% percent of the outcome up from 63.6% percent of implementation of partnership-funded projects which represents 0.8% increase.

Table 4.32: Comparison before and after introduction of moderating variable

Results	Before moderating	After moderating
R	.797 ^a	.803 ^a
R^2	.636	.644
F-Statistics	17.449	18.111
P-Value	.000 ^b	.000 ^b

From the findings of the study, it is clear that the introduction of the moderating variable (fund release condition) had an impact on implementation of partnership-funded projects as reflected by changes in R values, R^2 values and F-Statistics values.

Hypothesis Testing

The four research hypotheses that the study sought to test are addressed in this section based on regression analysis coefficient output on Table 4.28 and 4.31 above.

Project Planning and Implementation of Partnership-funded Projects

The result of the first hypothesis was achieved by testing H_{01}

H_{01} : Project planning has no statistically significant influence on the implementation of partnership-funded projects at KETRACO

The study findings revealed that project planning had positive and statistically significant effect on the implementation of partnership-funded projects at KETRACO with $\beta_1=0.188$ at P value 0.008 which is less than 0.05. It is on this basis the null hypothesis that project planning has no statistically significant influence on the implementation of partnership-funded projects at KETRACO is rejected. In addition, after introducing the moderating variable (fund release conditions) project planning was also found to have positive and statistically significant effect on the implementation of project management with $\beta_1=0.333$ at P value 0.027. The finding of the study concurred with Nyingi (2017), who concluded that plans are a cornerstone of any project and as so, planning is a dominant activity within a project context. Ondari (2013), postulate that during project planning, clarity of the early steps needs to be undertaken towards the realization of the long-term outcome. In highlighting the critical role planning plays in successful project implementation Gakobo (2017) contends that planning requires excellent forward planning, which includes detailed planning of the process implementation stages and milestones, task timeliness, fallback positions and re-planning.

Stakeholder Involvement and Implementation of Partnership-Funded Projects

The result of the second hypothesis was achieved by testing H_{02}

H_{02} : Stakeholders' involvement has no significant influence on the implementation of partnership-funded projects at KETRACO.

The study findings revealed that stakeholders' involvement had positive and statistically significant effect on the implementation of partnership-funded projects at KETRACO with $\beta_1=0.607$ at P value 0.000 which is less than 0.05. It is on this basis the null hypothesis that stakeholders' involvement has no significant influence on the implementation of partnership-funded projects at KETRACO is rejected. In addition, after introducing the moderating variable (fund release conditions) stakeholders' involvement was also found to have positive and statistically significant effect on the implementation of partnership-funded projects with $\beta_1=0.667$ at P value 0.000. The finding of the study asserts earlier study done by Yusoff (2015), who analyzed the various factors which are critical to the success of a project most which were centered on managing stakeholders. He propounded that stakeholder participation right from the onset of the project is critical as it ensures that the community owns up the project which is viewed as one of the factors that could ensure project success. Therefore effective implementation of partnership-funded projects is done with the participation of these stakeholders.

Technical Skills and Implementation of Partnership-funded Projects

The result of the third hypothesis was achieved by testing H_{03}

H_{03} : Technical skills have no significant influence on the implementation of partnership-funded projects in KETRACO.

The study findings revealed that technical skills had positive but statistically insignificant effect on the implementation of partnership-funded projects at KETRACO with $\beta_1=0.029$ at P value 0.649 which is greater than 0.05. It is on this basis the null hypothesis that technical skills have no significant influence on the implementation of partnership-funded projects in KETRACO is accepted. In addition, after introducing the moderating variable (fund release conditions) technical skills was also found to have positive but statistically insignificant effect on the implementation of partnership-funded projects with $\beta_1=0.412$ at P value 0.284. The finding of the study is in line with study conducted by Meredith & Mantel (2017), who noted that successful project managers were seen as having relevant experience or knowledge about the technology required by the project, however rarely were effective project managers seen as technical specialists since knowledge and proficiency in certain specialized field is needed to accomplish specific tasks. A research conducted by Mwanzia (2014) concluded that technical expertise does not correlate directly to successful implementation partnership-funded projects. The study advocates that reliance solely on "technical expertise" was found to be limiting because it restricted flexibility and alternatively having an open mind to cast the net wider and amass knowledge on other spheres. Technical skills capability as opined by Njenga (2017) indicates that it really depends on the type and size of projects, their structure, resources available, and the project environment.

Management Leadership and Implementation of Partnership-Funded Projects

The result of the fourth hypothesis was achieved by testing H_{04}

H_{04} : Management leadership has no significant influence on the implementation of partnership-funded projects in KETRACO.

The study findings revealed that management leadership had positive and statistically significant effect on the implementation of partnership-funded projects at KETRACO with $\beta_1=0.406$ at P value 0.000 which is less than 0.05. It is on this basis the null hypothesis that management leadership has no significant influence on the implementation of partnership-funded projects in KETRACO is rejected. In addition, after introducing the moderating variable (fund release conditions) management leadership was also found to have positive and statistically significant effect on the implementation of partnership-funded projects with $\beta_1=0.583$ at P value 0.001. The finding of the study concurred with an earlier study on the effect of leadership on construction projects in public secondary schools in Tana River County, Kenya which was done by Ongesa (2012). The findings of this study strongly indicated a positive relationship between the managements' leadership styles and successful completion of those projects.

According to Shore (2015), leadership affects corporate culture, project culture, project strategy, and project team commitment.

The regression equation for this study before the introduction of moderating variable can be stated as: $Y = -0.401 + 0.188X_1 + 0.607X_2 + 0.029X_3 + 0.406X_4 + \epsilon$ Where Y is implementation of partnership-funded projects while X_1 , X_2 , X_3 and X_4 represents project planning, stakeholder involvement, technical skills and management leadership respectively. A low coefficient of technical skills 0.029 implies that even though technical skills of project managers is a factor that influence implementation of partnership-funded at KETRACO project the impact is minimal. This can be supported by the fact that KETRACO can hire staff with technical knowhow to undertake specific projects. In addition, even with technical skills if these managers do not plan effectively and if the community is not involved in project implementation the project may not succeed. Moreover, without effective leadership the projected may also fail due to lack of clear guidance in achieving the goals. This implies that with proper planning, community involvement and effective leadership, implementation of KETRACO will still be effective since technical expertise can be hire when appropriate.

The regression equation for this study after the introduction of moderating variable can be stated as: $Y = -2.167 + 0.333X_1 + 0.667X_2 + 0.417X_3 + 0.583X_4 + \epsilon$ Where Y is implementation of partnership-funded projects while X_1 , X_2 , X_3 and X_4 represents project planning, stakeholder involvement, technical skills and management leadership respectively. After, incorporating moderating variable the coefficient for all independent variables were enhanced implying that fund release condition play a significance role in enhancing implementation of partnership-funded projects.

V. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of the Study Findings

This research aimed at establishing the factors affecting the implementation of partnership-funded projects at Kenya Electricity Transmission Company (KETRACO). The specific objectives of the study were to evaluate the influence of project planning, stakeholders' involvement, technical skills and management leadership on the implementation of project management in partnership funded projects at KETRACO. In addition, the study also intended to assess the moderating effect of the fund release conditions on implementation of partnership-funded projects.

5.2.1 Project Planning and Implementation of Partnership-Funded Projects

Objective one of the study sought to assess the influence of project planning on the implementation of partnership-funded projects. Descriptive statistic revealed that project managers normally prepare master project plan before implementing KETRACO projects and the project teams were included in the planning of the project schedule. In addition, the findings revealed that planning of the project activities start from the project definition stage where the planning policies and procedures are shared to relevant stakeholders even though the budget estimates in the project plan are not strictly adhered to during implementation. Despite all the effort to plan in advance the projects were also found to start and finish on time. Multiple regression revealed that there was a positive and significant linear relationship between project planning and the implementation of partnership-funded projects with a slope of 0.406 at p value of 0.000. Moreover after incorporating the moderating variable project planning had a positive and significant effect on the implementation of partnership-funded projects with a slope of 0.583 at p value of 0.001.

5.2.2 Stakeholder Involvement and Implementation of Partnership-Funded Projects

Objective two of the study sought to assess the influence stakeholders' involvement on the implementation of partnership funded projects.

Descriptive statistic revealed that that stakeholder do participate in implementation of partnership-funded projects to a large extent. In addition, the findings revealed that even though there were active engagements of stakeholders which could lead effective implementation of projects the opportunities were not adequately created for local people to actively participate in various activities during implementation. This may be attributed to failure to adequately undertake review and analysis of stakeholders when undertaking and implementing projects. Multiple regression revealed that there was a positive and significant linear relationship between stakeholders' involvement and the implementation of partnership-funded projects with a slope of 0.029 at p value of 0.649. Moreover after incorporating the moderating variable stakeholders' involvement had a positive and significant effect on the implementation of partnership-funded projects with a slope of 0.417 at p value of 0.284.

5.2.3 Technical Skills and Implementation of Partnership-Funded Projects

Objective three of the study sought to establish the influence of technical skills on the implementation of partnership funded projects. Descriptive statistic revealed that most of the staff had the required technical skills to implement partnership-funded projects which had influence on the implementation of partnership-funded projects to a moderate extent. In addition, the findings revealed that on average half of the respondents opined that that technical skill is critical determinant of how project activities are carried out hence project managers should have relevant experience or knowledge about the technology required by the project else they should be trained regularly on application of logic in order to perform their duties. Multiple regression revealed that there was a positive but insignificant linear relationship between technical skills and the implementation of partnership-funded projects with a slope of 0.607 at p value of 0.000. Moreover after incorporating the moderating variable technical skills had a positive but insignificant effect on the implementation of project management with a slope of 0.667 at p value of 0.000.

5.2.4 Project Planning and Implementation of Partnership-Funded Projects

Objective four of the study sought to determine the influence of management leadership on the implementation of partnership-funded projects. Descriptive statistic revealed that leadership influences the implementation of partnership-funded projects to a very large extent. In addition, the findings revealed that the project managers should be responsible for leading, building the skills of workers, encouraging innovation and empowering creative problem solving. It was also noted that leadership training is

essential to project managers in order to increase efficiency in implementing projects and variety of leadership styles should be applied when dealing with different challenges during project implementation. Multiple regression revealed that there was a positive and significant linear relationship between management leadership and the implementation of partnership-funded projects with a slope of 0.188 at p value of 0.008. Moreover after incorporating the moderating variable management leadership had a positive and significant effect on the implementation of partnership-funded projects with a slope of 0.333 at p value of 0.027.

5.3 Conclusion of the Study

The main objective of the study was to establish the factors affecting the implementation of partnership-funded projects at Kenya Electricity Transmission Company (KETRACO). The study revealed that project planning ;stakeholders' involvement and management leadership had positive and statistically significance influence on the implementation of partnership-funded before and after incorporating moderating variable. This implies that implementation of partnership-funded projects at KETRACO greatly influenced by project planning, stakeholders' involvement and management leadership. The study therefore concludes that there should be effective project planning before and during project implementations. In additions, stakeholders need to be involved from the initial process of project design up to the last stage of project review and monitoring. Leaders should be trained in order to increase their efficiency in project management to enable them use different of leadership styles when dealing with different challenges during project implementation.

Technical skills had positive but statistically insignificance influence on the implementation of project management before and after incorporating moderating variable. This implies that technical skills lead to improved implementation of partnership-funded projects though the effect is not paramount as compared to other variables considered by the study. The study therefore concludes that the project managers should possess relevant knowledge and experience about the technology required in order to execute their duties during implementation of partnership-funded projects.

Based on the finding, the study also conclude that moderating variable (Funds Release Conditions) had a positive impact on the on the implementation of partnership funded projects at KETRACO.

5.4 Recommendations of the Study

A number of recommendations can be made. The study findings show that improvement in project planning, stakeholders' involvement and management leadership had a positive and statistically significant effect on the implementation of project management in partnership funded projects at KETRACO. The study therefore recommends that project planning should start at initial stage of concept development where the team should come up with master plan which needs to be reviewed regularly. This study recommended that there should be policies to ensure those stakeholders' involvements in all projects developments and locals are given opportunities to actively participate in activities that may not require technical skills.

The study further recommend that project managers and leaders should be trained in order to increase their efficiency in project management to enable them use different of leadership styles when dealing with different challenges during project implementation.

5.5 Suggestions for Further Research

This research makes a significant contribution in our understanding on the factors affecting the implementation of partnership-funded projects at KETRACO. Arising from this research, the researcher makes several recommendations for further research. Conduct a research focusing on the benefits of stakeholders' involvements during the entire cycle of project development and implementations. Future researchers might as well adopt a case study research design for other sector other than energy sector that would further add value in understanding the factors affecting the implementation of partnership-funded projects. This study considered four variables, project planning, stakeholders' involvement, technical skills and management leadership. Future researchers should also focus on other types of composite variables of that may influence the implementation of partnership-funded projects.

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